

A STUDY ON UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS' SENSITIVITY TOWARDS SEX IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

There has been an unprecedented transformation and revolution in human culture in the 21st century which cut across all sphere including sexual values. This transformation has also been noticed in consensual unions over the last few decades in many developed countries in the West most especially among students in the university (Blom et al 1993, Bumpass et al 1991, Kiernan 1996). This has given birth to a culture of cohabitation, and there is a growing trend of cohabitation and premarital sexual intercourse since the 1960s (Scherrer & Klepacki 2004; Musick 2007). The changing trends in the social life of Nigerian of recent have made many practices like cohabiting in higher institutions in shared hostels an accepted norm. Several studies which looked at the impact of cohabitation of unmarried couples have been conducted and there is uniformity in their result which shows higher risk of marital disruption, disruption in education pursuit, unstable family background (Bumpass & Sweet, 1989), and lower commitment to the institution of marriage (Bennett et al. 1988). Also, various degree of association has been found between premarital cohabitation and divorce in Europe (Svarer, 2004, Liefbroer & Dourleijn, 2006) and USA (Phillips & Sweeney 2005, Teachman, 2002, Kamp, Dush, Cohan, & Amato 2003).

Key words: Sexual behaviour, perception, transformation, Nigeria.

Introduction:

Studies have shown that the campus environment impacts student perception and behaviour and has become part of their academic occurrence (Astin, 1975; Pascarella & Terenzini, 1980 &

1991; Tinto, 1987). Though there are researches that have empirical evidence to show that sexual harassment is a pervasive social problem in Nigerian university campuses (Owuamanam, 1990; Aba, 1992; Denga, 1996; Adamolekun, 2003) but researchers found that the Nigerian students' views of what constitutes sexual harassment differ from the western view simply in terms of strictness and cultural mores which make Nigerians regard behaviours like subtle pressure and sexist remarks about a woman's body irrelevant to sexual harassment. The University of Ibadan in 2012 put in place a sexual harassment policy to guide both the students and staffs in the way they relate with each other in the campus. The University due to shortage in hostel facility has two of her hostel facilities accommodating both female and male students. There is dearth of information on the perception of students of the University of Ibadan on male and female students living together in the same hostel. This study therefore assesses the sexual behaviour and perception of undergraduate students of University of Ibadan towards cohabitation in the campus.

Methodology

Study design

The study was a descriptive cross-sectional design that assesses the perception of undergraduate students of University of Ibadan on cohabitation and their sexual behavior in the campus.

Study site

The UI was established in 1948 and as such, it is the oldest tertiary institution in Nigeria, the foundation students began their courses at Ibadan on 18 January 1948. The University is located on the northern edge of the city of Ibadan (7° 20'N, 30° 50'E) in a campus of about 10.4 square kilometres. There are thirteen Faculties in the University namely: Arts, Science, Basic Medical Sciences, Clinical Sciences, Dentistry, , Pharmacy, Forestry, the Social Sciences, Agriculture, Education, Public Health, Veterinary Medicine, Technology and Law. The University has 12 Halls of residence for students namely Mellanby, Kutu, Sultan Bello, Tedder, Independence, Nnamdi Azikiwe, Queen Elizabeth, Queen Idia, Obafemi Awolowo, Tafawa Balewa, Alexandra Brown and the New Postgraduate Halls. Out of these, two are exclusively for post-graduate

students; one is a mixture of both the undergraduate and post-graduate students while the others are for the undergraduate students. Also two of the undergraduate halls are a mixed hall for both male and female students.

Instrument for data collection

The instrument for data collection was a self-administered semi-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire for the study was design to gain insights into the perception of undergraduate students of University of Ibadan on cohabitation in the hostel in the campus.

Sampling Technique

The University of Ibadan has ten (10) undergraduate halls. One is a mixture of both the undergraduate and post-graduate students; one is mix gender while others are single gender hostel. Three undergraduate halls were randomly selected (one from each of the category recognized) A proportional sampling technique was then used to select 400 consenting respondents to fill the pretested questionnaires. The questionnaire employed both open and closed-ended questions; it was designed to be self-administered and the main criterion for inclusion in the study was that a respondent is an undergraduate student of the University. The questionnaire was divided into three (3) sections. The first section asked on personal data of the respondents. The second section assessed of sexual behaviour of respondents and the third section focused on perception on mix gender in halls of residence and rooms. A total of 400 questionnaires were administered and 332 (83%) of these questionnaires were retrieved. The completed questionnaires were checked for completeness and open-ended questions were coded. The data was analyzed with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 15.0 using descriptive statistics, chi-square at 0.05 significant level.

Ethical consideration

The respondents that were recruited for this study were intimated with the process, nature, objectives and purpose of the study after which verbal consent was obtained from those who were agreed to participate in the current study. All the respondents were assured of

confidentiality, anonymity and privacy of information provided and giving the choice not to partake in the study if they so desired and as many that agreed were recruited for the study.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

More of the respondents (52.7%) are resident in Idia hall, 25% are in 200 level of their study and 76.2% are females. More (76.2%) respondents were Christian, majority (96.7%) were single and 55.8% of them agreed that there are four (4) occupants living in a room. Also, 79.8% reported that they have opposite sex as siblings; 26.3% agreed that they live with siblings of opposite sex in the same room with 21.7% of them reported that they enjoy time living with the opposite sex in the same room and 49.4% agreed that they would support the idea that male and female live together in the same halls of residence

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Socio-Demographic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Halls of residence		
Idia Hall	175	52.7
Awolowo Hall	114	34.3
NnamdiAzikiwe Hall	43	13.0
Faculty		
Arts	47	14.8
Science	74	23.3
Basic medical sciences	27	8.5
Pharmacy Public	3	.9
health Agric and	2	.6
forestry	39	12.3
Social science	31	9.8
Education	50	15.8
Technology	22	6.9
Law	19	6.0
Vet. medicine	2	.6
Institute	1	.3
Total	317	100.0
Sex (n=332)		
Females	253	76.2
Males	79	23.8
Geo-political zone (n=324)		
South- west	176	54.3
South- East	84	25.9
South-south	33	10.2
North East	23	7.1

North Central	7	2,2
Foreigner	1	.3
Age (years) (n=313)		
<18yrs	27	6.7
>18yrs	292	93.3
Total		
Mean age= 21.1±2.9yrs		
Religion (n=313)		
Christianity	253	80.8
Islam	56	17.9
African Traditional Religion (ATR)	18	1.0
Eckanka	1	.3
Level of study (n=327)		
100	65	19.6
200	83	25.0
300	82	24.7
400	65	19.6
500	15	4.5
600	3	.9
700	13	4.2
Marital status (n=329)		
Single	318	96.7
Married	8	2.4
Cohabiting	1	.3
Widowed	2	0.6

Fig. 1 Respondents who have siblings of opposite sex

Fig.2. Respondents who share room with siblings of opposite sex

Fig.3. Number of students in a room

Sexual Behaviour

A total of 62.7% agreed that they have boy/girlfriend. A little above half (53.1%) of the respondents reported that their partner is a student of UI; out of these, 64.5% agreed that their partners do visit them in their rooms and 76.4% reported this act as welcoming to their roommates. Few (14.5%) had ever had clash with their roommates due to their partners visit. Less than a quarter (18.0%) reported that they had ever allowed their partners to pass the night with them in their rooms and 56.3% of them said that their roommates did not complain about it. More than a quarter (35.2%) of the respondents agreed that they had ever seen students of opposite sex passing the night in their hall. A total of 32 (10.8%) respondents agreed that there are rooms in the hall where male and female students live together. Reasons adduced for this practice includes: promote inter-gender relationship (29.7%); increased premarital sexual intercourse (16.0%); makes residence lively (13.7%) (Table 2). More respondents (61.5%) agreed that they had ever been invited to visit their partner in his/her room. Also, 32.2% reported that their partner had ever requested them to pass the night with him/her in his/her room and 72.6% of them accepted the invitation. More than a quarter (29.0%) of the respondents agreed that they had ever had sex with their partners in the halls of residence and 71.2% of them said that the sexual episode was unprotected; 69.6% of those that use protection use condom and 52.9% agreed that they used this protection to prevent pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and 75.4% said they always use their choice form of protection. A total of 124 (40.1%) of the respondents reported that opposite sex do visit their halls outside the official hour of visitation and 44.1% of the respondents would want the rules guiding the movement of opposite sex in the halls be reviewed.

A total of 42 (13.7%) of the respondents had ever witness sexual harassment in their halls and out of this, 75.0% reported that sexual harassment often happen in evening/night time in the halls. Few (5.8%) had ever been sexually harassed in their halls of residence. More than a quarter (37.5%) reported that they have been victims of sexual harassment in the day time/afternoon in the hall. Also, 14.9% reported that their friends/roommate had complained to them about sexual harassment in the hall and 55.9% of them advice their friend to report officially to the school

authority. Less than half (42.6%) of the respondents would support the idea of mixed gender living in the same hall.

Table 2: Respondents' reasons for mixed gender in halls of residence

s/n	Response	Frequency	Percentage
1	It promote inter-gender relationship	63	29.7
2	It increased premarital sexual intercourse	34	16.0
3	It makes residence lively	29	8.7
4	It increased sexual harassment	28	8.4
5	It is improper	28	8.4
6	It disrupt privacy	13	6.1
7	Indifferent	15	7.1
8	It decreased homosexuality	1	.3

Fig.4. Advice giving by respondents to friends who were sexually harassed in the Hall

Perception on cohabitation

Several questions were asked to know the perception of respondents on cohabitation among students of the UI. More than quarters (33.1%) of the respondents are of the opinion that both male and female students should be allowed to visit each other at anytime in the hall; 9.1% are of the view that it is alright if a female is being sexually harassed in a male hostel likewise a male in the female hostel and 20.8% agreed that female should be blamed for sexual harassment in the halls (Table 3)

Table 3: Respondents perception on cohabitation

s/n	Statement	Agreed (%)	Disagreed (%)
1	Male and Female should live together in the same hall	47.7	52.3
2	Party involving both males and females should be organised at anytime in the hall	39.6	60.4
3	Male and Female should be allowed to visit each other at anytime	33.1	66.9
4	I can allow the opposite sex to pass the night in my room as long as his/her partner in my room	28.0	72.0
5	Allowing both sex to live together would increase the incidence of sexual harassment	54.5	45.5
6	It is alright if a female is being sexually harassed in a male hostel likewise a male in the female hostel	9.1	90.9
7	Female should be blamed for sexual harassment	20.8	79.2

Discussion

More of the respondents are females and resident in Idia hall because the hall has the highest number of undergraduate students out of the halls selected for the study and it is a female hall; more were in the second year of their study may be due to the fact that they are the ones that agreed to be part of the study at the time of visit to the hall. The result also shows that majority were Christians, this is because the southern part of Nigeria which majority of the respondents comes from are Christians (Pew Research Center's Forum on Religion & Public Life, 2010). Virtually all the respondents were single and more are within 19-23 years old; this may be due to the fact that the educational system in Nigeria is such that people are expected to spend a minimum of 16 years (6-3-3-4 system of education) in school as such most students though of marriageable age are still single because of longer years to complete their schooling. The implication of this is that you find sexually active young adult in school engaging in risky sexual behaviour (Olaseha, Ajuwon & Onyejekwe 2004). More than half of the respondents agreed that they are four (4) occupants living in the room; this may be due to the fact that the rooms in the halls are in categories based on the size (some have two (2) occupants while some have four (4) occupants) and students are allocated to them based on their level of study. More than a quarter of the respondents agreed that they live with siblings of opposite sex in the same room, this may be due to the fact in Africa and Nigeria in particular culture do encourage siblings to live together. Another possible reason for this may be the poverty level in the country where it is established that more than 63% of the inhabitant lives on less than \$1 daily (World Bank, 2011).

Sexual Behaviour

Majority of the respondents were single and between the ages range 18-21 years with more than half of them reporting to have boy/girlfriend. This is revealing and may not be unexpected since studies have shown that most students are young people and across countries, this stage of development is characterized by sexual interests and experimentation based on risky behaviour

(Turner, 1998; Lowenstein 1991; Kassirer, 1997; Santelli, 1998; Gutierrez, 2000; Whitaker, 2000; Davis 2000; Omoteso, 2006). Majority of those in a relationship agreed that their partners do visit them in their rooms and their roommates see this as welcoming, this may be due to the guiding rule in the hostel that allowed opposite sex to visit at certain hours of the day depending on the hostel. Though few of the respondents had clashed with their roommates but the study did not asked of the actions taken. It shows that it is not all the students that are in support of the act of opposite sex visitation in the hostel.

It is interesting to know that 18% of the respondents had ever allowed their partner to pass a night with them in their rooms and some agreed that there are rooms in the halls where male and female students live together. This may be made possible because the rooms in most of the halls are not being routinely checked to know if there are unauthorized occupants in the rooms. It might also be that some of the respondents are residents in mixed halls (male and female students live in the same hall) making it easier for cohabitation in the hall. This practice is alien to African culture and it is seen as taboo for unmarried people to cohabit. In recent time the African culture where chastity had been held in high esteem had been replaced by the adoption of western lifestyle, since in these Western countries cohabitation is now a normative stage in the family life course and a lifestyle among students and the working youth, who not only choose to share their lodgings, but also their blankets (Bumpass & Lu 2000; Smock 2000; Dolbik-Vorobei, 2005; Murray-Swant, 2005). The authority should see to it that effective means is put in place to make sure that rules that guide residents in the halls are strictly adhere to in order to guide against issues like this.

Various reasons were given by respondents for cohabiting in the halls; these include promote inter-gender relationship, increased premarital sexual intercourse and liveliness of residence. These reasons corroborate reasons given by young people in United States America (USA) who were asked reasons people might want to cohabit (National Survey of Families and Households, 2008). Other studies have revealed affection and attraction as top reasons why most young people cohabit (Surra & Hughes 1997; Prager 2000). More of the respondents agreed that they had ever been invited to their partners room, this, the rules guiding the movement of opposite sex allowed, provided such visit is within the visiting hour but more than a quarter of them reported that their partners had ever requested them to pass the night with them in their rooms in the hall contrary to the university rules of which 72.6% of them accepted the invitation. This further confirm the assertion that some of the students in the university environment being away from home for the first time do engage in sexual experimentation especially without parental supervision. Also, the liberal atmosphere of the university community further encourages this experimentation which may lead to sexually transmitted infection (STIs) and unwanted pregnancies and the predicament of dealing with the ensuing problems may be enormous (Cadmus & Owoaje, 2010).

The result shows that unprotected sex was been practice by majority of those that are sexually active. This is consistent with previous findings among young people including university students (Cadmus & Owoaje, 2010; Adinma & Okeke, 1995; Oye –Adeniran, Adewole, Umoh & Oladokun, 2005; Ebuehi, Ekanem & Ebuehi, 2006; Imaledo, Peter-kio & Asuquo, 2012).

Condom is more popular as a form of protection among sexually active though few of them uses it. This finding corroborate previous studies both in Nigeria and elsewhere which reveals that condoms is the most popular of all contraceptive device though it's use is still abysmally low (NDHS) among the sexually active (NDHS, 2008; Huber & Ersek, 2009; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2009; Lewis et al., 2007; Campbell et al., 1992; Rotermann, 2005 and Rahamefy, Rivard, Ravaoarino, Ranaivoharisoa, Rasamindrakotroka & Morisset, 2008). It is also interesting to note that a little above half of the respondents that use condom did so as a means of prevention of pregnancy and STI this is contrary to the study carried out among college students in America which shows that a higher percentage of students did not choose to use condoms to prevent sexually transmitted disease (STDs); but more are concerned with preventing pregnancy than the spreading of STDs which portend danger considering the consequence of such an action (Murray & Miller, 2000).

The result of this study also revealed that majority of those that use protection always use their choice form of protection. This corroborate the findings of Murray and Miller, (2000) where 88% of their respondents who are college students 'very often' used condoms to prevent unwanted pregnancies, however, the findings of this study is at variance with the finding of Maurice carried out in Democratic Republic of Congo among university students in 2010 which revealed that consistent use of the condom was low among their study respondents.

A total of 124 of the respondents reported that opposite sex do visit their halls outside the official hours of visitation. This may be due to the weak enforcement of rules relating visiting hours for the opposite sex in the halls. There is the need for concern authority to put in place measures to address this trend among the students most especially when a male is found in the female hostel at the odd times/hours, this can generate a lot of tension among the female students. This also shows that the present system in the halls need to be reviewed since unlawful practices are going on in the halls considering the number of respondents that have seen opposite sex in their halls outside the approved hours of visitation. Worthy of note is that some of the respondents want the rules guiding the movement of opposite sex in the halls be reviewed. This shows that there is an urgent need to review the rules and ensure that residents in the halls abide by these rules.

Few of the respondents have witnessed and few have also been victims of sexual harassment in their halls of residence. This confirms the assertion of previous studies that sexual harassment perpetrated by students is more common than sexual harassment perpetrated by teachers and other staffs in the university. Although previous studies had focused on teachers/students relationship (AAUWEF, 1993; Lee, Croninger, Linn & Chen, 1996; Fineran & Bennett, 1998; Adamolekun, 2003). It is expected that sexual harassment often happens in the evening/night time; this is because there are not lectures in most Nigerian Universities after 6pm and before 6am and most students would have retired to their rooms, reading rooms or library to rest, read or revise previous class work, making the halls almost deserted and perpetrators can take advantage of this to harass any opposite sex found in the halls at such an hour. This finding also corroborate the findings of Bayram and Dinç in Turkey which shows that health students reported that they are mostly subjected to sexual harassment during watch duty/night shift (between 4 pm– 8am) (Bayram & Dinç, 2012).

More than half of the respondents reported that they advise their friend who were sexually harassed to report officially to the school authority. This is expected of them since the university has a policy against sexual harassment (University of Ibadan Sexual Policy, 2012). The victims of sexual harassment to a large extent have been able to remain silence and bear it alone because according to Denga and Denga (2004), the advent of cultism on university campuses seems to have aggravate sexual harassment in Nigeria universities as victims would rather prefer to endure the ordeal of peer sexual harassment than risk the retaliatory actions of sexual harassers, who most of the time, are members of campus cults.

It is worthy to note that a little less than half of the respondents would support the idea of mixed gender living in the same hall. This may be due to the fact that such a practice is strange to Africa culture and the policy of the university does not allow or permit undergraduate students in the halls to practice cohabitation though mixed gender is allowed in two undergraduate halls.

Perception towards cohabitation

The result shows that there are different perceptions towards cohabitation expressed by the respondents. More than quarters are of the opinion that both male and female students should be allowed to visit each other at anytime in the hall. This may be due to the fact that most young people in the universities in Nigeria see themselves as been matured and as such there is no situation they cannot handled and there is also a growing trend amongst African young people to think that it is unfashionable if they do not experiment with sex before marriage as been practiced in the developed western countries as popularized through the electronic media. Young people perceive pre-marital sexual experimentation as part and parcel of modernity and would want to familiarize themselves with matters concerning sexual intercourse before they get married.

Few of the respondents are of the view that it is alright if a female is being sexually harassed in male hostels likewise a male in the female hostels. There is the possibility that some of these respondents see sexual harassment as fun in the hall and some of them may not know the physical and psychological implication of it. It may also be that some of these respondents are not aware that the university has a policy against sexual harassment which carries some sanctions if established to be carried out by the perpetrator on campus.

The result also shows that some of the respondents agreed that females should be blamed for sexual harassment in the halls. This corroborates previous assertion that there is the individuals' likelihood of sexually harassing correlated with their rape myth acceptance (which involves attributions that the victim desires sexual coercion) and low perspective taking ability (Pryor, 1987) and that sexual harassment is more likely to be dependent when the initiator's behaviour is more clearly sexual (Thomann & Wiener, 1987). This finding might be that men consider gender harassment as trivial and seductive behaviour as acceptable forms of sexual approach (Fitzgerald & Ormerod, 1991).

Implication of findings and conclusions

The noticed risky sexual behavior among the study population exposes them to STI including HIV/AIDS with deadly consequences. The University of Ibadan has witnessed series of AIDS prevention activities however there is the need to review the methodology and the operation of these programs in order to be able to reduce to the barest lowest level risky sexual behavior practices in the halls of residence.

Since the result of this study reveals that students are breaking the official visiting hour, the rules guiding the visiting hours in the halls need to be reviewed and the personnel that are responsible for the enforcement need to be retrained on how to ensure that students keep to the visiting hour rules and ensure that those who float the rules are made to face the consequence.

Also, it was noticed in this study that some of the participants have negative perception on sexual harassment. This calls for the need to include sexual harassment in the school curriculum of the students in their first year of study. This is to expose them early to the consequence of such an action and what the university policy says about it. Early education on sexual harassment will in no small way help to set the new student on the right path during their stay in the University.

Conclusion

The undergraduate students of the University of Ibadan exhibit some level of risky sexual behaviour and there are also negative perceptions about sexual harassment in the halls of residence. There is the need for renewed effort by school authority and other stakeholders to collaborate and to make available more hostel facilities that could accommodate the growing student population and intensify effort in continuous sensitizing and educating students on the danger of risky sexual behavior and the consequence of sexual harassment since the University has an existing policy on sexual harassment.

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